

Annex III

History of Extrasolar Access

Annex to Kingmakers: life's gateway to the stars

CONTENTS:

The *Annex III History of Extrasolar Access*, is investigating the potential impact life on Earth might have had historically out of the Solar System, when defined as considered in *Annex I Solar System*. From an argumentative viewpoint, in the perspective defended in *Kingmakers, life's gateway to the stars*, the kingmaker position of humans is critically dependent on the hypothesis along which “life has had no historical possibility of interstellar access”. This annex is detailing elements discussing this hypothesis, which are synthesized in *Kingmakers, life's gateway to the stars, III,D, Beyond Solar*.

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Introduction

After introducing the subject of life access to extrasolar space (1), we here investigate the history of the different processes constitutive of this access.

Using the speed of transmission as an interpretative key, we will start by incidental (2), then intentional (3) potential impacts of the Solar System originated life, to the extrasolar environment, by signals travelling at lightspeed. These impacts will be considered as dependent upon the hypothesis of the existence of extrasolar intelligent life (ETI-dependent).

We will then proceed with the investigation of potential impacts happening at slower speeds, investigating access to the extrasolar environment via physical transfers involving exchanged materials (4), and probes (5).

No synthesis nor conclusion are proposed to this annex as a section synthesizing the work proposed here, is available in Kingmakers, life's gateway to the stars, III.D) *History of extrasolar access*.

1- Access to outer space

Since its first beginnings on Earth, the descending causality inherent to Earth originated biodiversity has been flowing through the Universe, beyond Earth itself, and even beyond the Solar System:

First, by modifying the terrestrial surface and atmosphere, along the past billions of years, life repeatedly changed the composition of the atmosphere and ocean, and consequently, the emissions and reflectivity of the planet. This signal could have been picked by anybody looking for it. Reiproqually, picking up such a signal from another planet is precisely what our exobiologists are dreaming of. Should there have been anybody out there, there is at least some probability that this signal was not missed.

Then, biologic elements such as RNA and even cells and microorganisms might have been exchanged inside the Solar System, with other celestial bodies following collisions¹. It may be imagined that through a similar process, such bricks of life have been expelled at velocities beyond the Solar System escape speed. Also, calculation showed gravity may have eject material as big as giant planets, out of our Solar System². As such, the possibility exists that

¹ XXX Ref Required

² See expelled materials

right now, elements of Earth originated life are travelling at interstellar distances. Who knows: following this reasoning, such elements might even have contributed to, or supplanted, the evolution of other lifeforms in extrasolar stellar systems³, this being a classical proposition in the panspermia hypothesis regarding the origin of life on Earth..

About a hundred years ago, a range of perfectly new elements were added to the spectrum, with the invention of radio transmission. From this moment, the outbound flow seems to increase at an exponential rate, and soon, probes are escaping the gravity well of the Solar System, carrying messages to aliens. Intentional messages are sent at lightspeed to would-be civilisation in faraway galaxies. Contaminated robots are roaming everywhere in the home system. Various junk including a wheel of cheese, a political manifesto, not to forget Musk sportscar, start orbiting our Sun. A box containing humane DNA and dehydrated extremophiles organisms named tardigrades, crashes on the moon. Time capsules of all kinds, promising to convey an incredible variety of elements, including data, dna, and even organism, across extreme lengths of time, are popping up everywhere around, to be eventually picked up and by future civilisation and/or would-be galaxy-roaming aliens, then capable of instantiating and distributing some of the included elements. Through these processes, the extraplanetary access of life related causality has been dramatically increased, and seems accelerating out of control.

Having settled the context, we will in the sections below explore the incidental and intentional signals that might have been picked up, and possibly been influencing lifeforms beyond our solar environment, should these exist. Then, the question of physical exchanges with extrasolar bodies will be explored, investigating the question of the ejection of matter following collisions and gravitational ejection, alongside with the question of the probes that have been sent by mankind, beyond our stellar environment.

2- incidental signals

When it not absorbed by the environment, the energy carried by omnidirectional signals is decreasing as a function of $1/(4\pi r^2)$. Here below are to my understanding the most significant undirected signals outbound from the Solar System, alongside with their date of emission. The possible direct and ET-dependent impact of these signals seems minimal, while the ETI-impact

³ Something that could be envisioned considering the resistance of life as defended in the main document, and the interaction of new coming species with existing ones, as proposed by [1] (Mooney and Cleland 2001) The evolutionary impact of invasive species

could be really high. We humans appear not accountable for their vast majority, until the beginning of agriculture.

Table 1. An overview of incidental signals

Date	Signal
About -4,5 billions year	<p>A planet is aggregating in the Solar System, that will eventually lay in the habitable zone. This signal could be detected by agents searching for it, just as we do right now looking for habitable exoplanets, as on the example below of the HR 8799 system, directly imaged by us humans from a distance of 129ly</p> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>Direct imaging of HR 8799 system <i>(animation not visible on printed and pdf versions, link)</i></p> </div>
From -3.7 billion year	<p>The spectral signature of Earth is changed due to the reworking of its oceans atmosphere and crust by lifeforms. A proposed biomarker is the oxygen rise during the great oxidation event, 2.4 Gy ago. The colonisation of land masses by land plants, 0.5 Billion years ago, might also be of interest;</p>
From -10.000 years	<p>The spectral signature of Earth, is abruptly changed due to the human development of agriculture</p>
From -100 years	<p>First radio transmissions leak to outer space, and since then, dramatic increase.</p>

a) The potential for habitability

Before life itself could have an impact, its potentiality might have had one. In a similar way to which the humans findings about planets within the habitable zone of their stars, popped open a copernican revolution regarding the character of exception of the Solar System, the sole information of our planet existing within the habitable zone of the Sun, might have been of importance for extrasolar observers.

The farthest detected exoplanet related with potential habitability, as for the moment this thesis is written, is MOA-2011-BLG-293, as identified from NASA exoplanet catalog. It was discovered using the microlensing method, in 2011. This gaseous giant is lying in the habitable zone of its

star, which means it could have habitable moons⁴. Impressingly, it is really far away in the galaxy. Its stellar system is located in the galactic bulge, 25.100 lightyears away. If we consider that the exoplanet detection range we humans achieve today, to be a good proxy to the minimal detection capability of a would be ETI, then reciprocally, the potential for Earth habitability could have been identified, as a minimum, from such a distance.

From the averaged 100-400billion stars in the milky way, and from the drawing below, where the positions are derived from the GAIA catalog via the Nasa exoplanet app, I propose a rule of thumb estimation of a minimum of 25-100 billions stellar system from which a would be ET could pick up the Solar System potential for habitability, in present time⁵.

Over its ~4.5 Billions years of existence, with a galactic orbital period of 225-250My the Solar System has revolved ~20 times, and has hence been overtime sweeping with its habitability detectability range, the entire galaxy, whose components are rotating asynchronously with the Solar System, with the last sweep happening in the last ~250My.

Various methods have been developed for identifying exoplanets. One element to consider, that might minor the above thumb estimation, is that one of the two methods leading to the most distant discoveries, which is the methods of transits, require the host star and the planet to detect, to be at some point aligned with the receiving telescope. This means that the receiver has to be located very close to the ecliptic plane of the Solar System. The ecliptic happens to make a $\pm 60^\circ$ angle with the galactic plane. Consequently, the locations susceptible to picking up our signature using this method are limited to where the ecliptic plane intersects: a slice in the galactic disc, as presented in the shema below. The ecliptic precession period⁶ is negligible against the galactic period, and as a consequence, at galactic scale, no preferred region may be identified for detectability, due to this effect. Fig 1. Below, is representing such locations from which technologies similar to ours, could identify the Solar System as being habitable.

⁴ [2] ([Batista et al. 2013](#)) [moa-2011-blg-293lb: first microlensing planet possibly in the habitable zone](#)

⁵ Using the GAIA archive, the estimation is of a minimum of 156 millions systems. This has to be considered as an underestimation, consistent with the average proposed above of 25-100 billion, due the archive not being exhaustive at these distances.

⁶ To verify, 27.000 years.

Fig 1. Locations from which technologies similar to ours, could identify the Solar System as being habitable.

Positions and distances in the galaxy, to scale,
from the NASA exoplanet catalog, accessed via EXOPLANET⁷ app.

b) The signature of life

Biomarkers refer to elements indicating the existence of life. The first possible impact of Solar System life beyond the boundaries of the Solar System itself, could be to an extraterrestrial civilisation such as ours, uncertain about the existence of life elsewhere in the universe, to detect life on Earth. Interestingly, exobiologists, lacking an example of extraterrestrial life, have been extensively working to understand what in the history of life on Earth, could be noticeable from outer space. On Earth, a proposed detectable biomarker is the permanent rise of atmospheric oxygen from as low as 0.001% to detectable levels (20%), occurring 2.4Gyr ago, resulting from first photosynthesizing oceanic organisms and known as the great oxidation event.⁸

⁷ Nasa exoplanet catalog, accessed 15/09/20 from [exoplanet app](#).

⁸ [3] (Lyons et al. 2014) [The rise of oxygen in Earth's early ocean and atmosphere](#)

Fig 2. Evolution of Earth's atmospheric oxygen content through time⁹

Two methods are identified amongst today's technology that might allow for the identification of such gaseous biomarkers: the analysis of transit spectrums, and direct imaging. The farthest exoplanet positively identified with the transit method, within the habitable zone of its star, is KIC9663113b, distant from 5400ly, about ten times farther away than the farthest planet identified with direct imaging, CHXR73-B, which is only 600ly away, and not in the habitable zone of its star.

The detection of the Solar System by similar technologies to ours appears consequently more probable within a 5400ly radius (Comprehending 59 million stars, as per GAIA catalog), on the intersect between the Solar System ecliptic plane and the galactic plane and within 600ly (comprehending a minimum of 1.1M stellar systems¹⁰), elsewhere. With a rule of thumb estimation of 0.1% of the 5400ly radius to intersect sufficiently with the Solar System ecliptic to provide a transit analysis of the atmosphere leading to the identification of biomarkers (leading to 59.000 potentially detecting systems), we find that biomarkers will more probably be detected by direct observation than by any other methods, in present time. ~1M stellar system could presently detect life on Earth from biomarkers, with ~present technology.

The sweeping period for detectability due the planetary precession of the Solar System (27.000years), and the information transit time (5400years) being neglected against the Galactic period (225-250My), the swept volume of detectability over the presence of biomarkers on Earth ends up being a torus, small radius 5400ly, large radius 2600ly¹¹ swept ~15 times in life history on Earth. With the hypothesis of a stellar density similar to the GAIA density 5400ly around us, the conclusion is that over time, detection of life on Earth with ~present technology could have happened from 1billion stellar systems.

⁹ [3] (Lyons et al. 2014) The rise of oxygen in Earth's early ocean and atmosphere

¹⁰ From GAIA Archives

¹¹ Volume of a torus $2\pi^2 R r^2$

Fig 3. Locations from which technologies similar to ours, could have identified biomarkers in the Solar System

Positions and distances in the galaxy from the NASA exoplanet catalog, accessed via EXOPLANET app¹². CAUTION: the intersection between galactic plane and ecliptic plane of the Solar System, has not been calculated and is only depicted as an artist's view¹³. The rest of the schema is to scale.

Gaia stars, >2000K, in radius 5400ly	Density star/ly ³	Volume torus(ly ³)	Stellar systems possibly identifying biomarkers in Earth atmosphere, with similar technology to us, in Earth history
59202954	8.98E-05	1.44E+13	1.29E+09

¹² Nasa exoplanet catalog, accessed 15/09/20 from [exoplanet app](#).

¹³ Sorry for that, BTW

c) Radio Leakage

Unintentional signaling ranges from omnidirectional signals, whose power decreases very quickly with distance r , as $1/4\pi r^2$, to very directional ones, broadcasted directionally, but only randomly in the direction of the potential eavesdropping receiver. The more directional the signal is, the higher the distance reached for a given transmitting power. The thing is, the less it is likely to be aiming at a place where an eavesdropping listener could be. More: more powerful, undirected directional signals are likely to be received during a shorter time by an eavesdropping receiver, due to the rotation of the transmitter and the relative displacement of the receiver, hence lowering the available integration time.

Optimistic calculations made around the pro-METI conversation end up with a possible detection of our artificial electromagnetic leakage by a civilisation with a similar advance to ours, up to 100pc (316ly), with telescopes the size of the SKA (Square Kilometer Array)¹⁴, but neglect the required integration time for the signal, and when accounted for this parameter, SKA size telescope wouldn't be able to detect present leakage beyond 50ly.¹⁵

it appears to some authors that radar tracking systems used in radar astronomy, due to their widespread usage, are, while unintentionally, a million time more likely to reach out to a potential listener, than the intentional signals investigated later¹⁶, and hence, that no special consideration should be given to the intentional METI signals. Invalidating this calculation is the fact that the vast majority of those signals are limited to where targets are to be tracked in the Solar System *ie* in the ecliptic plane¹⁷, which is 63° off the plane of the galaxy, hence not where the potential receiving stars are located.

The literature regarding the detectability of the unintentional broadcast from Earth appears to classify in two factions, where the scientific discussion seems highly impacted by the underlying point of view regarding the below detailed METI effort (Messaging Extraterrestrial Intelligence). Indeed, the detectability of the existing unintentional broadcast is a critical argument for or against the innocuity of METI: "we've already been signaling anyway !" Going through this literature, it appears that while the science more or less agrees on range for a given receiver, much of the argumentation holds on the postulated receiving capability and efforts of the would

¹⁴ [4] (Loeb and Zaldarriaga 2007) Eavesdropping on radio broadcasts from galactic civilizations...

¹⁵ [5] (Billingham and Benford 2011) Costs and Difficulties of Large-Scale 'Messaging'...

¹⁶ [6] (Zaitsev 2008) Detection Probability of Terrestrial Radio Signals by a Hostile Super-civilization

¹⁷ [5] (Billingham and Benford 2011) Costs and Difficulties of Large-Scale 'Messaging'...

be ET: METI-ists assume very advanced receiver, with ET investing huge resources, like for example space telescopes using gravitational lensing from 550 AU away from the home star.¹⁸ while the opposite faction holds on human style developpement for ET to ensure that: “Historical leakage from Earth has been undetectable as messages for credible receiver systems”¹⁹.

Using retrieved stellar distance to the Solar System²⁰ from the paralaxes of the second dataset from GAIA mission²¹, we find that the amount of stellar systems with $T_{\text{eff}} > 2000\text{K}$, possibly picking up our electromagnetic leakage, is of 1007 stars²² with the above mentioned corrected estimation for the range of leakage to be 50ly, or 241.000 stars, when considering the 325ly range proposed by pro-METIsts . The most recent and somehow impressive SETI(Search for extraterrestrial Intelligence) survey²³, which investigated 10 billion stars positioned by the GAIA registry, encountered no sign of intelligent life. We propose that the probability that our historical leakage has been picked up, is extremely low, and may be considered to be under 2%, with certainty, and of less than 0.01%, when the 50ly leakage pickup distance is considered, not forgetting that probability may even be orders of magnitude below, due to ET not necessarily looking for us.

The probability of our electromagnetic leakage to have been picked up may consequently be considered as close to null.

3- intentional signals

Directed signals are different by nature, because these, by being directed, do not suffer from the intensity decrease as $1/R^2$, nor the issue of random pointing. This gives them a way higher range for a given energy input. Table 2, below, lists the intentional, directed signals that have been sent by mankind. We decided to order these by the date of first possible feedback, meaning the earliest date at which we should receive a response to these signals, should something be replying, when considering the time of transit of the signal (moving at C).

¹⁸ [7] [\(Gertz 2016\) Reviewing METI: A Critical Analysis of the Arguments](#)

¹⁹ [5] [\(Billingham and Benford 2011\) Costs and Difficulties of Large-Scale 'Messaging'...](#)

²⁰ [8] [\(Bailer-Jones et al. 2018\) Estimating distances from parallaxes...](#)

²¹ [9] [\(Gaia Archive 2020\)](#)

²² [9] [\(Gaia Archive 2020\)](#)

Query to [GAIA catalog](#): SELECT source_id, r_est, teff_val FROM external.gaiadr2_geometric_distance JOIN gaiadr2.gaia_source USING (source_id) WHERE r_est < 15 and teff_val > 2000 ORDER BY r_est ASC

²³ [10] [\(Tremblay and Tingay 2020\) A SETI survey \[...\]Orders of magnitude expansion in search space](#)

Table 2. List of directed signals, by date of first possible feedback

Including hyperlink to wikipedia ressources, when existing

Message	Destination	Distance (ly)	Time since sent (Y)	Date sent	Date of first possible feedback	Date of first possible feedback at 20% <i>c</i>
RuBisCo Stars	SO J025300.5+16 5258	13	11	2009	2035	2087
RuBisCo Stars	GJ83.1	15	11	2009	2039	2099
Sónar Calling GJ273b	Luyten's Star	13	3	2017	2043	2095
Sonar Calling 2	Luyten's Star	13	2	2018	2044	2096
Lone Signal	HD119850	18	7	2013	2049	2121
A Message From Earth	HIP74995	21	12	2008	2050	2134
Altair (Morimoto - Hirabayashi) Message[20]	Alpha Aql	34	37	1983	2051	2187
Hello From Earth	HIP74995	21	11	2009	2051	2135
Cosmic Call2	HIP4872	33	17	2003	2069	2201
RuBisCo Stars	GJ137	30	11	2009	2069	2189
Cosmic Call2	HD245409	37	17	2003	2077	2225
Cosmic Call2	HD75732	41	17	2003	2085	2249
Cosmic Call2	HD 10307	41	17	2003	2085	2249
Teen Age Message	HD95128	46	19	2001	2093	2277
JAXA Space Camp (UDSC-1)	HD75732	40	7	2013	2093	2253
Wow! Reply	HD75732	41	8	2012	2094	2258
JAXA Space Camp (UDSC-2)	HD75732	40	6	2014	2094	2254
Cosmic Call2	HD95128	46	17	2003	2095	2279
CNES COSMIC CONNECTION		45	14	2006	2096	2276

DORITO		46	12	2008	2100	2284
Cosmic Call1	HD190360	52	21	1999	2103	2311
Teen Age Message	HD 76151	56	19	2001	2113	2337
Cosmic Call1	HD190406	58	21	1999	2115	2347
Teen Age Message	HD 126053	58	19	2001	2117	2349
Teen Age Message	HD 193664	58	19	2001	2117	2349
Wow! Reply	HD50692	57	8	2012	2126	2354
Cosmic Call1	HD178428	68	21	1999	2135	2407
Cosmic Call1	HD186408	70	21	1999	2139	2419
Teen Age Message	HD197076	69	19	2001	2139	2415
Wow! Reply	HIP34511	151	8	2012	2314	2918
NASDACosmic-Colleg e	Alpha Vir	250	23	1997	2497	3497
Across the Universe	HIP11767	431	12	2008	2870	4594
A Simple Response to an Elemental Message	HIP11767	434	4	2016	2884	4620
Teen Age Message	HD50692	3056	19	2001	8113	20337
Hommage à Stephen Hawking		3500	2	2018	9018	23018
Arecibo Message	NGC 6205	20181	46	1974	42336	123060
Morse Message			58	1962		???

An interesting element to note is a trend in the choice of targets, towards closer ones. The 1974 Arecibo message, mainly a philosophical manifest, was targeted a cluster 20 billions lightyears away, with a first possible feedback, extremely unlikely due to the distance, 40 thousands years ahead. As a comparison, recent messages sent in the framework of METI (Messaging Extraterrestrial Intelligence), or active SETI (Search for extraterrestrial intelligence), are conceived as “active sonar” detection of extraterrestrial life, and engineered methodically with the purpose of obtaining a feedback, should there be one to wait for. The latest message, Sonar Calling²⁴, has been shot at a target located only 13 lightyears away, to a system where

²⁴ [11] ([Sonar calling, 2020](#))

two planets have been discovered, including the super Earth, GJ 273 c (Luyten c), located in the habitable zone of its star, hence possibly sustaining life as we know it.

This trend is confirmed when looking up figure 4. Proposed below : messages are sent to closer and closer targets, and the 100 years ahead are to see a lot of possible feedback.

Fig 4. Date of first possible feedback to METI signals as a function of date sent

Amongst the above 38 identified METI directed signals, very little have been targeting the real establishment of a communication, hence problems like targeting, diffusion and power have been overlooked. Overall, before 2011, intentional messages have been “faint and very unlikely to be detected, even by very nearby stars.”, with the most powerful of these messages, *cosmic call 1*, send in 1999, to have a decoding range of about 20ly, and a signaling range of 600ly²⁵, should it have been looked at with a square kilometer telescope. The later 8 messages, Wow! Reply (1,2,3) ,2012 ,Lone Signal (2013),JAXA Space Camp(1&2)(2013), A Simple Response to an Elemental Message(2016), and Sonar Calings (1,2)(2017-2018), have been constructed in a more precise way, and may today be considered as more detectable.

To my understanding, regarding METI signals, both Meti-ist, and anti-Meti-ists, have interest in their argumentation, to demonstrate far ranging capability. The first ones, with the goal of motivating investors, the second ones, for the purpose of demonstrating the dangers of METI.

²⁵ [5] (Billingham and Benford 2011) Costs and Difficulties of Large-Scale 'Messaging'...

As a consequence for this, I propose that the calculated ranges for detectability of METI signals, as found in the literature, are probably high-range estimates.

Using GAIA archives in a similar manner as in the preceding section, we find 1.1 million stellar systems to be in range, for the detection of the energy of a transmission such as cosmic call1, and only 82 of these, at distances below which such a signal could be decoded, should the received be listening to it with a square kilometer telescope.

Given the total of 9 such transmissions up to today, the absence of known intelligent life, and the fact that it might even not been listening to it, should it exist, let alone with such a big instrument as a square kilometer telescope, I propose that the probability that any information originated on Earth has become extrasolar, is close to null.

4- gravitational ejection

In 2017, *Oumuamua*, an unidentified object, went from the interstellar space, across the Solar System. While a very wide array of possibilities have been formulated regarding its origin, including the one of an extraterrestrial probe, the most probable hypothesis emerging today appears to be the one of an asteroid, expelled by an extrasolar stellar system²⁶. Asteroids are not the only objects possibly expelled by a system, and according to computer simulations, the laws of physics allow for objects as big as a giant planet the size of Uranus or Neptune, to have been expelled from our own system²⁷. The increasing detection of free floating planets, (about twenty candidate rogue planets have been identified up to now²⁸) could be a possible indication that this type of ejection is rather common. Also, considering as developed in *Annex I, Solar System*, that 12 stellar system travel through ours every million year, and consequently that ~ 54.000 have flown through it since its debuts, with a ~5% probability of one of these flying within the Kuiper belt²⁹, it is reasonable to consider that some ejection has possibly occurred.

a) Interstellar

In this context, such bodies, possibly carrying information, bricks or even forms of life on top of their significant mass and energy, might have been providing the Solar System outbound causality with long range capability . Also, when physics allows for the ejection of a giant planet,

²⁶ Ref Required. XXX

²⁷ [\(Nesvorný 2011\) \(Nesvorný 2011\) Young solar system's fifth giant planet?](#)

²⁸ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Rogue_planet#Known_or_possible_rogue_planets

²⁹ See *Annex I Solar System, 5, Exotic futures*, and [12] [\(García-Sánchez et al. 2001\) Stellar encounters with the solar system](#)

there is little doubt on whether a small object, such as Elon musk sportscar carrying the Arch Mission Foundation “Solar Library”, could end up catapulted to the extrasolar space at some point in the future.

b) Intergalactic

With the recent identification of the ejection of a main sequence star, S5-HVS1, twice the mass of the Sun, out of our galaxy at a speed of 1700km/s ($\sim 0.6\%c$), by our galaxy center black hole³⁰, I propose the hypothesis along which such ejections might play a role in the natural spread of life, not only inside our galaxy, but also across intergalactic distances). At such a speed, the collapsing part of Virgo supercluster ($\sim 3e7ly$ radius), distant of ($\sim 3e7ly$), could be reached in $\sim 7Gyr$ (calculations made with a de Sitter model), which as envisioned in *Annex I Solar System*, could permit the survivability of life along the way provided that the movement of the habitable zone is followed by life, along the aging of the star, and provided that cataclysmic stellar events are not to happen in the timeframe. $\sim 1e15$ Solar masses³¹ are estimated to be lying the gravitationally bound structure of Virgo Supercluster, the closest to our galaxy and its future merger with m31-M3, while the gravitationally bound local group only holds $2e12 M_{\odot}$, and is to become eventually causally separated from Virgo SC. As a consequence, somehow hopping on such an intergalactic travelling stellar system could be an opportunity for the Milky Way originated life, to expand its opportunities by a factor of ~ 500 . The hills mechanism theories the ejection of stars by galaxy center black holes, and recent studies conclude that observed HVS (High Velocity Stars) are consistent with such an hypothesis³². More, extragalactic ejection is observed to happen from outer places in the galaxy, as observed in the case of LAMOST-HVS1, ejected at 550km/s ($0.2\%c$) from the Norma spiral arm.³³

5- Probes

Earth originated life, thanks to mankind, has now sent 4 probes with extrasolar ambitions, two of these, Voyager 1 and 2, being at this moment beyond the heliopause . At Voyager 1 speed, the farthest probe today, the closest stellar system would be reached within 40.000 years, should it had been aimed in this direction. More, while intrinsically impressive, the reached

³⁰ [13] [\(Koposov et al. 2019\) Discovery of a nearby 1700 km s⁻¹ star ejected by Sgr A*](#)

³¹ [14] [\(Chon et al. 2015\) On the definition of superclusters](#)

³² [15] [\(Brown et al. 2018\) Gaia and the Galactic Center Origin of Hypervelocity Stars.](#)
Continuous ejection proposed in [\(Brown\) Hypervelocity Stars and the Galactic Center](#)

³³ [16] [\(Hattori et al. 2019\) Origin of a Massive Hyper-runaway Subgiant Star...](#)

distance is only the heliopause, which is located at a ridiculous 0.07% of the radius of the Solar System when defined from its gravitational influence. The fastest moving objects produced by mankind, are only to leave the Solar System gravitational influence 50 to 60.000 years from now.

No man-made originated object has ever travelled beyond the Solar System gravitational limits, as defined by the sphere of influence.

Table 3. Would-be extrasolar probes

	Date sent	Distance (UA)	Distance to exit Solar System (UA)
Voyager 1	5 septembre 1977	145	204664
Voyager 2	20 août 1977	116	204693
Pioneer 11	6 avril 1973	97	204712
Pioneer10	3 mars 1972	90	204719

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